

Database of the endangered architecture 1945–2000

The *Database of the endangered architecture 1945–2000*¹ is a freely available dataset licensed under the Creative Commons BY-NC-SA 4.0 International license². It consists of sites mainly in the Czech and Slovak Republics that are at risk of demolition or reconstruction, built between 1945 and 2000. The source for our data is the Facebook group *Ošklivá architektura*³ or the Internet.

For each location, we try to recollect additional data, such as a specific location characterized by address and geographic coordinates, the author (s), dates of construction, and the state of danger. Other columns, for example, are for reference links, links to photographs (we tend to upload our photographs to the Wikimedia Commons repository and add them to Wikipedia or Wikidata), and others.

We subjectively assess the buildings to the following categories: endangered (when there is a discussion or proposal to demolish the building), critically endangered (when there is information that the building might be demolished in a short period of time), demolition (when the building is being demolished), and reconstruction (when the building is being reconstructed). Demolished or fully reconstructed buildings are then moved to the archive (in Czech *Archiv*).

The dataset is available in Google Sheets for filtering or downloading. It is written in Czech. The first line provides information on how to cite the Database and lists the contributors. Mr. Lochman first published it in 2020 as a pure list, and over time, it evolved into its current format. It is updated continuously, and the reader can find the most recent update for each line in the column called *Aktualizace (d/m/r)* (in English, Updated (d/m/y)). The second line provides the information on the license and a technical contact. The third line of the *Aktuální* tab is the names of different columns.

The *Database of the endangered architecture 1945–2000* could be found via the following link:
https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1X6dnzgJ161L8C-KC775kEX7vhYmgkCYTu_GNCV0tce4/edit?usp=sharing

1 Link to the dataset: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1X6dnzgJ161L8C-KC775kEX7vhYmgkCYTu_GNCV0tce4/edit?usp=sharing

2 Full text available online: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/deed.en>

3 Available via: <https://www.facebook.com/groups/OsklivaArchitektura>